

Using Fractional Taylor Series Expansion to Solve Some Limit Problems

Chii-Huei Yu

School of Mathematics and Statistics, Zhaoqing University, Guangdong, China

Abstract In this paper, some limit problems are studied by using the fractional Taylor series expansions of several fractional functions. A new multiplication of fractional analytic functions is introduced, which is a natural extension of the multiplication of traditional analytic functions.

Keywords Limit problems, Fractional Taylor series expansions, Fractional functions, New multiplication, Fractional analytic functions

1. Introduction

Fractional calculus is a branch of mathematical analysis which deals with the research and applications of integrals and derivatives of arbitrary order. In recent decades, the field of fractional calculus has attracted the interest of researchers in diverse scientific fields such as mathematics, physics, chemistry, engineering, and economics [1-12]. In this article, we use a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions and the method of fractional Taylor series expansion to study the following five limit problems:

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{[\sin_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha})]^{\otimes 3}}{x^{3\alpha}}, \quad (1)$$

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{x^{3\alpha} \otimes E_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha})}{\frac{2}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}x^{\alpha} - \sin_{\alpha}(2x^{\alpha})}, \quad (2)$$

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\sin_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}) \otimes [1 - \cos_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha})]}{x^{3\alpha} \otimes \cos_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha})}, \quad (3)$$

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\frac{2}{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)}x^{2\alpha} - [\sin_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha})]^{\otimes 2}}{1 - \frac{3}{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)}x^{2\alpha} - [\cos_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha})]^{\otimes 3}}, \quad (4)$$

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{[\sin_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha})]^{\otimes 2}}{[E_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}) - 1 - \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}x^{\alpha}] \otimes \cos_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha})}, \quad (5)$$

where $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, $(-1)^{\alpha}$ exists, and $E_{\alpha}, \cos_{\alpha}, \sin_{\alpha}$ are α -fractional exponential function, cosine function, sine function respectively. Moreover, the new multiplication \otimes of fractional analytic functions is a natural generalization of ordinary multiplication of analytic functions.

2. Preliminaries and Properties

Definition 2.1([13]): Suppose that x, x_0 and a_n are real numbers, $x_0 \in (a, b)$, and $0 < \alpha \leq 1$. If the function $f_{\alpha}: [a, b] \rightarrow R$ can be expressed as α -fractional power series, i.e., $f_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)}(x - x_0)^{n\alpha}$ on some open interval $(x_0 - r, x_0 + r)$, then $f_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha})$ is called α -fractional analytic at x_0 , where r is the radius of convergence about x_0 . If $f_{\alpha}: [a, b] \rightarrow R$ is continuous on closed interval $[a, b]$ and is α -fractional analytic at every point in open interval (a, b) , then we say that f_{α} is an α -fractional analytic function on $[a, b]$.

In the following, we introduce a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions.

Definition 2.2([13]): Assume that $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and $f_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}), g_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha})$ are two α -fractional analytic functions,

$$f_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)}x^{n\alpha}, \quad (6)$$

$$g_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^\infty \frac{b_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} x^{n\alpha}. \tag{7}$$

Then we define

$$\begin{aligned} f_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes g_\alpha(x^\alpha) &= \sum_{n=0}^\infty \frac{a_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} x^{n\alpha} \otimes \sum_{n=0}^\infty \frac{b_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} x^{n\alpha} \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^\infty \frac{1}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} \left(\sum_{m=0}^n \binom{n}{m} a_{n-m} b_m \right) x^{n\alpha}. \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

Definition 2.3 ([14]): Suppose that $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and x is a real number. The α -fractional exponential function, sine function and cosine function are defined as follows:

$$E_\alpha(x^\alpha) = 1 + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + \frac{1}{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)} x^{2\alpha} + \frac{1}{\Gamma(3\alpha+1)} x^{3\alpha} + \dots = \sum_{n=0}^\infty \frac{1}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} x^{n\alpha}, \tag{9}$$

$$\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha - \frac{1}{\Gamma(3\alpha+1)} x^{3\alpha} + \frac{1}{\Gamma(5\alpha+1)} x^{5\alpha} - \dots = \sum_{n=0}^\infty \frac{(-1)^n}{\Gamma((2n+1)\alpha+1)} x^{(2n+1)\alpha}, \tag{10}$$

$$\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha) = 1 - \frac{1}{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)} x^{2\alpha} + \frac{1}{\Gamma(4\alpha+1)} x^{4\alpha} - \frac{1}{\Gamma(6\alpha+1)} x^{6\alpha} + \dots = \sum_{n=0}^\infty \frac{(-1)^n}{\Gamma(2n\alpha+1)} x^{2n\alpha}. \tag{11}$$

Proposition 2.4 (fractional Euler’s formula) ([14]): Let $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, then

$$E_\alpha(ix^\alpha) = \cos_\alpha(x^\alpha) + i\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha). \tag{12}$$

Proposition 2.5 (fractional DeMoivre’s formula) ([14]): If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and n is a positive integer, then

$$[\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha) + i\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes n} = \cos_\alpha(nx^\alpha) + i\sin_\alpha(nx^\alpha). \tag{13}$$

3. Main Results

To obtain the major results in this study, we need two lemmas.

Lemma 3.1: Let $0 < \alpha \leq 1$ and x be a real number, then

$$[\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes 2} = \frac{2}{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)} x^{2\alpha} - \frac{8}{\Gamma(4\alpha+1)} x^{4\alpha} + \frac{32}{\Gamma(6\alpha+1)} x^{6\alpha} - \dots. \tag{14}$$

Proof Using fractional DeMoivre’s formula yields

$$[\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha) + i\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes 2} = \cos_\alpha(2x^\alpha) + i\sin_\alpha(2x^\alpha). \tag{15}$$

Hence,

$$\cos_\alpha(2x^\alpha) = [\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes 2} - [\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes 2} = 1 - 2[\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes 2}. \tag{16}$$

Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} &[\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes 2} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2} \cos_\alpha(2x^\alpha) \\ &= \frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2} \left[1 - \frac{4}{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)} x^{2\alpha} + \frac{16}{\Gamma(4\alpha+1)} x^{4\alpha} - \frac{64}{\Gamma(6\alpha+1)} x^{6\alpha} + \dots \right] \\ &= \frac{2}{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)} x^{2\alpha} - \frac{8}{\Gamma(4\alpha+1)} x^{4\alpha} + \frac{32}{\Gamma(6\alpha+1)} x^{6\alpha} - \dots. \end{aligned} \tag{Q.e.d.}$$

Lemma 3.2: If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$ and x is a real number, then

$$1 - \frac{3}{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)} x^{2\alpha} - [\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes 3} = -\frac{21}{\Gamma(4\alpha+1)} x^{4\alpha} + \frac{183}{\Gamma(6\alpha+1)} x^{6\alpha} + \dots, \tag{17}$$

and

$$[\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes 3} = \frac{6}{\Gamma(3\alpha+1)} x^{3\alpha} - \frac{60}{\Gamma(5\alpha+1)} x^{5\alpha} + \dots. \tag{18}$$

Proof Also by fractional DeMoivre’s formula, we have

$$[\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha) + i\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes 3} = \cos_\alpha(3x^\alpha) + i\sin_\alpha(3x^\alpha). \tag{19}$$

It follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \cos_\alpha(3x^\alpha) &= [\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes 3} - 3\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes [\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes 2} \\ &= [\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes 3} - 3\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes [1 - [\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes 2}] \\ &= 4[\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes 3} - 3\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha). \end{aligned}$$

Thus,

$$[\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes 3} = \frac{1}{4} [\cos_\alpha(3x^\alpha) + 3\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha)]. \tag{20}$$

And hence,

$$\begin{aligned} & 1 - \frac{3}{\Gamma(2\alpha + 1)} x^{2\alpha} - [\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes 3} \\ &= 1 - \frac{3}{\Gamma(2\alpha + 1)} x^{2\alpha} - \frac{1}{4} [\cos_\alpha(3x^\alpha) + 3\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha)] \\ &= 1 - \frac{3}{\Gamma(2\alpha + 1)} x^{2\alpha} \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{4} \left[1 - \frac{9}{\Gamma(2\alpha + 1)} x^{2\alpha} + \frac{81}{\Gamma(4\alpha + 1)} x^{4\alpha} - \frac{729}{\Gamma(6\alpha + 1)} x^{6\alpha} + \dots \right. \\ &\quad \left. + 3 \left[1 - \frac{1}{\Gamma(2\alpha + 1)} x^{2\alpha} + \frac{1}{\Gamma(4\alpha + 1)} x^{4\alpha} - \frac{1}{\Gamma(6\alpha + 1)} x^{6\alpha} + \dots \right] \right] \\ &= 1 - \frac{3}{\Gamma(2\alpha + 1)} x^{2\alpha} - \frac{1}{4} \left[4 - \frac{12}{\Gamma(2\alpha + 1)} x^{2\alpha} + \frac{84}{\Gamma(4\alpha + 1)} x^{4\alpha} - \frac{732}{\Gamma(6\alpha + 1)} x^{6\alpha} + \dots \right] \\ &= -\frac{21}{\Gamma(4\alpha + 1)} x^{4\alpha} + \frac{183}{\Gamma(6\alpha + 1)} x^{6\alpha} + \dots \end{aligned}$$

On the other hand, since

$$\begin{aligned} \sin_\alpha(3x^\alpha) &= 3[\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes 2} \otimes \sin_\alpha(x^\alpha) - [\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes 3} \\ &= 3[1 - [\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes 2}] \otimes \sin_\alpha(x^\alpha) - [\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes 3} \\ &= 3\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha) - 4[\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes 3}. \end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

It follows that

$$\begin{aligned} & [\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes 3} \\ &= \frac{1}{4} [3\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha) - \sin_\alpha(3x^\alpha)] \\ &= \frac{1}{4} \left[\left[\frac{3}{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)} x^\alpha - \frac{3}{\Gamma(3\alpha + 1)} x^{3\alpha} + \frac{3}{\Gamma(5\alpha + 1)} x^{5\alpha} - \dots \right] \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \left[\frac{3}{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)} x^\alpha - \frac{27}{\Gamma(3\alpha + 1)} x^{3\alpha} + \frac{243}{\Gamma(5\alpha + 1)} x^{5\alpha} - \dots \right] \right] \\ &= \frac{6}{\Gamma(3\alpha + 1)} x^{3\alpha} - \frac{60}{\Gamma(5\alpha + 1)} x^{5\alpha} + \dots \end{aligned}$$

Q.e.d.

We have the following main results in this paper.

Theorem 3.3: Suppose that $0 < \alpha \leq 1$ and $(-1)^\alpha$ exists, then

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{[\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes 3}}{x^{3\alpha}} = \frac{6}{\Gamma(3\alpha + 1)}, \tag{22}$$

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{x^{3\alpha} \otimes E_\alpha(x^\alpha)}{\frac{2}{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)} x^\alpha - \sin_\alpha(2x^\alpha)} = \frac{\Gamma(3\alpha + 1)}{8}, \tag{23}$$

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes [1 - \cos_\alpha(x^\alpha)]}{x^{3\alpha} \otimes \cos_\alpha(x^\alpha)} = \frac{3}{\Gamma(3\alpha + 1)}, \tag{24}$$

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\frac{2}{\Gamma(2\alpha + 1)} x^{2\alpha} - [\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes 2}}{1 - \frac{3}{\Gamma(2\alpha + 1)} x^{2\alpha} - [\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes 3}} = -\frac{8}{21}, \tag{25}$$

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{[\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes 2}}{\left[E_\alpha(x^\alpha) - 1 - \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)} x^\alpha \right] \otimes \cos_\alpha(x^\alpha)} = 2. \tag{26}$$

Proof $\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{[\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes 3}}{x^{3\alpha}} = \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\frac{6}{\Gamma(3\alpha + 1)} x^{3\alpha} - \frac{60}{\Gamma(5\alpha + 1)} x^{5\alpha} + \dots}{x^{3\alpha}} = \frac{6}{\Gamma(3\alpha + 1)}$. In addition, since

$$\begin{aligned} x^{3\alpha} \otimes E_\alpha(x^\alpha) &= \Gamma(3\alpha + 1) \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(3\alpha + 1)} x^{3\alpha} \otimes \left[1 + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)} x^\alpha + \frac{1}{\Gamma(2\alpha + 1)} x^{2\alpha} + \frac{1}{\Gamma(3\alpha + 1)} x^{3\alpha} + \dots \right] \right] \\ &= \Gamma(3\alpha + 1) \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(3\alpha + 1)} x^{3\alpha} + \frac{4}{\Gamma(4\alpha + 1)} x^{4\alpha} + \frac{10}{\Gamma(5\alpha + 1)} x^{5\alpha} + \dots \right]. \end{aligned} \tag{27}$$

And

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{2}{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)} x^\alpha - \sin_\alpha(2x^\alpha) &= \frac{2}{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)} x^\alpha - \left[\frac{2}{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)} x^\alpha - \frac{8}{\Gamma(3\alpha + 1)} x^{3\alpha} + \frac{32}{\Gamma(5\alpha + 1)} x^{5\alpha} - \dots \right] \\ &= \frac{8}{\Gamma(3\alpha + 1)} x^{3\alpha} - \frac{32}{\Gamma(5\alpha + 1)} x^{5\alpha} + \dots \end{aligned} \tag{28}$$

It follows that

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{x^{3\alpha} \otimes E_\alpha(x^\alpha)}{\frac{2}{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)} x^\alpha - \sin_\alpha(2x^\alpha)} = \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\frac{\Gamma(3\alpha + 1) \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(3\alpha + 1)} x^{3\alpha} + \frac{4}{\Gamma(4\alpha + 1)} x^{4\alpha} + \frac{10}{\Gamma(5\alpha + 1)} x^{5\alpha} + \dots \right]}{\frac{8}{\Gamma(3\alpha + 1)} x^{3\alpha} - \frac{32}{\Gamma(5\alpha + 1)} x^{5\alpha} + \dots}}{\frac{\Gamma(3\alpha + 1)}{8}}.$$

On the other hand, since

$$\begin{aligned} &\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes [1 - \cos_\alpha(x^\alpha)] \\ &= \sin_\alpha(x^\alpha) - \sin_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes \cos_\alpha(x^\alpha) \\ &= \sin_\alpha(x^\alpha) - \frac{1}{2} \sin_\alpha(2x^\alpha) \\ &= \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)} x^\alpha - \frac{1}{\Gamma(3\alpha + 1)} x^{3\alpha} + \frac{1}{\Gamma(5\alpha + 1)} x^{5\alpha} - \dots \right] \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{2}{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)} x^\alpha - \frac{8}{\Gamma(3\alpha + 1)} x^{3\alpha} + \frac{32}{\Gamma(5\alpha + 1)} x^{5\alpha} - \dots \right] \\ &= \frac{3}{\Gamma(3\alpha + 1)} x^{3\alpha} - \frac{15}{\Gamma(5\alpha + 1)} x^{5\alpha} + \dots \end{aligned}$$

And

$$\begin{aligned} &x^{3\alpha} \otimes \cos_\alpha(x^\alpha) \\ &= \Gamma(3\alpha + 1) \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(3\alpha + 1)} x^{3\alpha} \otimes \left[1 - \frac{1}{\Gamma(2\alpha + 1)} x^{2\alpha} + \frac{1}{\Gamma(4\alpha + 1)} x^{4\alpha} - \frac{1}{\Gamma(6\alpha + 1)} x^{6\alpha} + \dots \right] \right] \\ &= \Gamma(3\alpha + 1) \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(3\alpha + 1)} x^{3\alpha} - \frac{10}{\Gamma(5\alpha + 1)} x^{5\alpha} + \frac{35}{\Gamma(7\alpha + 1)} x^{7\alpha} - \dots \right]. \end{aligned}$$

It follows that

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes [1 - \cos_\alpha(x^\alpha)]}{x^{3\alpha} \otimes \cos_\alpha(x^\alpha)} = \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\frac{3}{\Gamma(3\alpha + 1)} x^{3\alpha} - \frac{15}{\Gamma(5\alpha + 1)} x^{5\alpha} + \dots}{\frac{1}{\Gamma(3\alpha + 1)} x^{3\alpha} - \frac{10}{\Gamma(5\alpha + 1)} x^{5\alpha} + \frac{35}{\Gamma(7\alpha + 1)} x^{7\alpha} - \dots}} = \frac{3}{\Gamma(3\alpha + 1)}.$$

Moreover, by Lemma 3.1 and 3.2, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} &\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\frac{2}{\Gamma(2\alpha + 1)} x^{2\alpha} - [\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes 2}}{1 - \frac{3}{\Gamma(2\alpha + 1)} x^{2\alpha} - [\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes 3}} \\ &= \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\frac{2}{\Gamma(2\alpha + 1)} x^{2\alpha} - \left[\frac{2}{\Gamma(2\alpha + 1)} x^{2\alpha} - \frac{8}{\Gamma(4\alpha + 1)} x^{4\alpha} + \frac{32}{\Gamma(6\alpha + 1)} x^{6\alpha} - \dots \right]}{-\frac{21}{\Gamma(4\alpha + 1)} x^{4\alpha} + \frac{183}{\Gamma(6\alpha + 1)} x^{6\alpha} + \dots} \\ &= \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\frac{8}{\Gamma(4\alpha + 1)} x^{4\alpha} - \frac{32}{\Gamma(6\alpha + 1)} x^{6\alpha} + \dots}{-\frac{21}{\Gamma(4\alpha + 1)} x^{4\alpha} + \frac{183}{\Gamma(6\alpha + 1)} x^{6\alpha} + \dots} \\ &= -\frac{8}{21}. \end{aligned}$$

Finally, since

$$\begin{aligned} &\left[E_\alpha(x^\alpha) - 1 - \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)} x^\alpha \right] \otimes \cos_\alpha(x^\alpha) \\ &= \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(2\alpha + 1)} x^{2\alpha} + \frac{1}{\Gamma(3\alpha + 1)} x^{3\alpha} + \dots \right] \otimes \left[1 - \frac{1}{\Gamma(2\alpha + 1)} x^{2\alpha} + \frac{1}{\Gamma(4\alpha + 1)} x^{4\alpha} - \frac{1}{\Gamma(6\alpha + 1)} x^{6\alpha} + \dots \right] \\ &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(2\alpha + 1)} x^{2\alpha} + \frac{1}{\Gamma(3\alpha + 1)} x^{3\alpha} - \frac{5}{\Gamma(4\alpha + 1)} x^{4\alpha} - \dots \end{aligned}$$

It follows that

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{[\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes 2}}{\left[E_\alpha(x^\alpha) - 1 - \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)} x^\alpha \right] \otimes \cos_\alpha(x^\alpha)} = \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\frac{2}{\Gamma(2\alpha + 1)} x^{2\alpha} - \frac{8}{\Gamma(4\alpha + 1)} x^{4\alpha} + \frac{32}{\Gamma(6\alpha + 1)} x^{6\alpha} + \dots}{\frac{1}{\Gamma(2\alpha + 1)} x^{2\alpha} + \frac{1}{\Gamma(3\alpha + 1)} x^{3\alpha} - \frac{5}{\Gamma(4\alpha + 1)} x^{4\alpha} - \dots}} = 2.$$

Q.e.d.

4. Conclusion

From the above discussion, we know that the fractional Taylor series expansion is an important method to evaluate the limit problems in this paper. Furthermore, the new multiplication of fractional analytic functions we used is a natural generalization of multiplication of classical analytic functions. In the future, we will make use of the new multiplication to study the engineering mathematics problems and fractional differential equations.

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